

URWPM(Sonagi Model) 202404260032 Dataset Sample Evaluation

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1 Introduction

This is Universal Rapid Weather Prediction Model(URWPM, Sonagi Model) result evaluation report. The following accuracy was obtained based on the 202404260032 prediction (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11069195>) obtained to date. Considering the difference in density between obtainable measurements and predictions, the fact that these results were obtained even with comparisons of only about 10% suggests good performance of the model.

2 Evaluation Result

2.1 1st Evaluation

Total 3274920 items with real world observation obtained 238219 items has been evaluated.

Item	Spearman R	Kendall τ	RMSE
Wind Speed	0.461	0.326	7.239
Temperature	0.562	0.402	8.468
Surface Layer Pressure	0.710	0.548	35.229
Relative Humidity	0.299	0.209	31.633

2.2 2nd Evaluation

Total 3274920 items with real world observation obtained 313773 items has been evaluated.

Item	Spearman R	Kendall τ	RMSE
Wind Speed	0.446	0.314	6.937
Temperature	0.576	0.413	8.467
Surface Layer Pressure	0.670	0.503	37.863
Relative Humidity	0.257	0.179	33.239

2.3 3rd Evaluation

Total 3274920 items with real world observation obtained 393300 items has been evaluated.

Item	Spearman R	Kendall τ	RMSE
Wind Speed	0.429	0.301	7.262
Temperature	0.593	0.426	8.674
Surface Layer Pressure	0.683	0.510	38.524
Relative Humidity	0.228	0.158	33.925

2.4 4th Evaluation

Total 3274920 items with real world observation obtained 469837 items has been evaluated.

Item	Spearman R	Kendall τ	RMSE
Wind Speed	0.422	0.295	7.493
Temperature	0.595	0.427	8.761
Surface Layer Pressure	0.682	0.507	38.709
Relative Humidity	0.222	0.154	34.126

3 Conclusion

1. Relative Humidity needs more parameter optimization.
2. With average obtained 10% from the sampled data, the prediction seems to fairly fit with the real world observation data.
3. More follow up evaluation will be added continuously.